

BRIDGING THE TESTABILITY ANALYSIS / TEST PROGRAM GAP

AN APPROACH THAT BUILDS ON THE NAVY'S INTEGRATED DIAGNOSTICS SUPPORT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

We in the defense industry are all facing the reality of reduced budgets. Now more than ever it is necessary to work efficiently and effectively and in a concurrent engineering manner when developing Test Program Sets (TPSs). An approach is presented that has the potential to develop the Test Program (TP) portion of the TPS utilizing the data supplied by the Navy's Integrated Diagnostics Support System (IDSS). The IDSS is an integrated set of software tools which span the life cycle of a system while effectively exchanging information between other engineering disciplines. The IDSS Weapon System Testability Analyzer (WSTA) aids in achieving system testability goals, and also provides a precomputed test strategy from which Figures of Merit (FOMs) associated with the diagnostic process are derived (Mean Time To Isolate; Mean Time To Repair; etc.). The precomputed test strategy and the model of the system may be forwarded to the test site where the IDSS Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem (ADS) will isolate failures to the faulty components or subsystems. The model of the system is provided since the ADS is not limited to the use of only the precomputed test strategy, but may also use on-line reasoners to diagnose faults. However, it is recognized that direct implementation of the test strategy provided by the WSTA for TPS applications is not likely since special classes of tests (safe to power on; etc.) and the ability to constrain sequences of tests for effective resource utilization are not presently supported in the tool. A new test program development process is proposed that will build on the integrated diagnostic approaches espoused by the IDSS. Key elements of the process are presented.

INTRODUCTION

Quite often, a significant amount of re-engineering or reverse engineering is involved during the TPS development process. This is mostly due to the inadequacy of the Item Under Test (IUT) source design data supplied to the test engineer or TPS developer. Test Requirement Documents (TRDs) are historically incomplete and done after the fact. Additionally, schematics do not necessarily provide insight into the functions performed by the IUT, and consequently do not provide much insight into the IUT testing requirements. The most efficient means of transferring data to the test engineer is in the form of electronic data capturing the design, testing, failure, and logistics information associated with the IUT. This data should be supplied by application of concurrent engineering mechanisms similar to those used within the IDSS framework.

BACKGROUND

The IDSS program was initiated in the mid 80's to provide the Navy and other services a non-proprietary set of weapon system design tools to affordably and efficiently implement an integrated diagnostics solution. Figure 1 depicts the IDSS Architecture.

The *Weapon System Testability Analyzer* (WSTA)^[1] tool uses a dependency model approach that is applicable to digital, analog, and non-electronic systems. The WSTA is an interactive Design For Testability (DFT) analysis and verification tool whose objective is to support achievement of measurable DFT goals. It also generates a test strategy^[2,3], or

fault isolation tree, that may be used to define the actual diagnostic process. Inputs to the WSTA detail the relationship between failure modes of the system and the tests used to detect the failure modes. In addition, hardware topology and logistics data are used by the WSTA.

FIGURE 1

The *Adaptive Diagnostic Authoring* (ADA) tool inputs the test procedures (for all tests in the WSTA-generated strategy) into the diagnostic data base. In addition, production rules may be entered by the test engineer. These rules supplement the dependency model relationships. Technical information and training data are also inducted into the ADA to provide consistent and coordinated diagnostic help. Digitized mechanical drawings, schematics, and parts lists may be entered into the Diagnostic Data Base and associated with the diagnostic strategy. Digitized training data also may be associated with the diagnostic strategy.

The *Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem* (ADS)^[4] tool is an intelligent troubleshooting aid which is located at each test site. In its production configuration, the ADS may be either hosted in a stand-alone device such as a Portable Maintenance Aid (PMA), in a device that is loosely coupled to the system, or it may be completely embedded. For the most part, the ADS software is generic, with system-specific information found in the Weapon Data Base created by the ADA tool. The ADS contains logic to utilize the diagnostic resources (BIT, augmented BIT, guided manual troubleshooting, technician inputs, sequential replacement) that will have the most likelihood of success based on the diagnostic results up to that point. The

ADS design philosophy is to keep the technician in control of the diagnostic process and provide insight to him. The ADS provides the technician with a recommended next best test or a recommended repair action, in addition to any technical information he may require to effect the task at hand. The ADS also provides a running estimate of how long the diagnostic process will take to complete. If the situation demands a quick turnaround of the system, the technician may elect to take a less economical repair action. The ADS remembers its successes and failures and has the ability to automatically "adapt" its strategy in real-time. Logistics parameters (such as actual component failure rates) may be updated based upon the experience gained from previous diagnostic sessions.

The *Feedback Analyzer* (FA) tool periodically accepts information transferred from the Weapon Data Base to a central location for further processing and to enable "learning." It collects data from each of the ADS sites and performs a statistical analysis of these data to determine if a site's experience is globally valid or is merely valid for that particular site. In the former case, failure rates and test times contained within the Common Diagnostic Data Base (CDDB) are updated. Data are also collected from the maintenance shops that will indicate if suspect units were really faulty, re-tested OK, or were just good units in an ambiguity group. Finally, if a technician in the field had entered a suggestion that will be generally useful, that suggestion may be re-entered as a production rule using the ADA tool. In addition to being used to improve diagnostic procedures and strategies, the feedback data may also be used to justify engineering changes to the system's hardware to improve its testability, or to identify weaknesses in the supporting documentation and technician's training.

THE CONCEPT

Employing the dependency models created during the weapon system design using the WSTA, it appears technically feasible to automatically generate Test Programs (TPs) to detect and isolate faults at the Intermediate and Depot levels of maintenance. However, to make effective use of the models, the concept requires that expert system diagnostic capabilities be

resident within the ATE stations utilized at these maintenance sites. Potential benefits of this new approach to developing TPs include the following:

- Consistently high quality TPs will be generated. This will be achieved by early attention to typical quality measures such as:
 - Test Coverage
 - Ambiguity Group Distribution
 - Test Efficiency

Also, utilizing a thoroughly analyzed model of the IUT along with a proven diagnostic engine will ensure predictable and consistent results.

- Overall Test Program Set (TPS) development time would be drastically reduced due to the elimination of manually created test strategies and the definition of a minimal set of required tests.
- The time and cost to detect and isolate faults should be reduced due to the generation of efficient test strategies. Furthermore, due to the adaptive nature of the diagnostic reasoner, TP execution could improve in time, i.e., the Mean-Time-To-Detect / Mean-Time-To-Isolate should further decrease as the TP gains more "intelligence".
- As dependency modeling technology matures and component and subsystem libraries are developed, TPS development times and costs will be further reduced. These reductions will be consistent with the industry trend toward re-use of software / data components and subsystems.

THE CHALLENGE

The present configuration of the IDSS System falls short of implementing the total solution to the above concept for the following reasons:

- The IDSS was conceptualized and implemented as an "Organizational-Level Solution", i.e., the main objective of the IDSS program was to increase system

readiness. This premise allowed the IDSS developers to make the following assumptions: (1) that the weapon system would include all the necessary Built-In-Test (BIT) mechanisms / procedures to effectively detect faults, and (2) based on the first assumption, that the IDSS fault isolation engine, or the ADS, could assume the presence of a fault. These assumptions are not necessarily appropriate for the Intermediate and Depot levels of maintenance.

- The Intermediate and Depot Maintenance Levels have the requirement to certify units returned for repair as Ready-For-Issue (RFI). Certification, or performance verification, entails running functional, or end-to-end tests, without failure. Since the IDSS system has no mechanism to distinguish between Fault Detection tests and Fault Isolation tests, the unit cannot be certified as RFI efficiently.
- The ADS presently has no mechanism to intelligently handle tester resources. When conducting dynamic fault isolation, the fault isolation sequence is not known a priori. How tester resources are handled is critical to the resultant fault isolation time, i.e., due to real-world situations such as tester switching and warm up times. A reasoner is required to determine the optimum balance between minimized tester overhead and minimized fault isolation time.

THE APPROACH

Enhanced Test Strategies. As discussed earlier, test strategies generated by the IDSS WSTA tool are based on a Fault Isolation (FI) objective. However, a robust test environment must accommodate not only the fault isolation test sequencing strategy, but also a Fault Detection (FD) test strategy. See Figure 2. FI strategies would have to be modified / enhanced in order to support functional testing at the Intermediate and Depot maintenance levels. The approach is to provide tools and / or features that fit into the IDSS framework in order to implement the new test strategies.

Encapsulated Test Programs (ETPs). Fundamental to the new test program development process are Encapsulated Test Programs (ETPs). ETPs have the following properties:

- they are atomic tests that provide a pass/fail result to a diagnostic reasoner;
- each atomic test ideally provides 100% coverage of the associated failure modes;
- the tests are written in a manner that makes them transportable between host tester platforms; and
- the atomic tests provide the necessary information to allow intelligent tester resource management.

For on-line reasoners to operate effectively, the tests must be allowed to execute in virtually any

order. However, complete encapsulation of test programs must be recognized as being inherently inefficient in terms of resource utilization, with a corresponding time inefficiency. This is readily seen in the example of two consecutive tests applying and removing power and ground. The obvious solution is to keep these signals applied between the tests. Thus, mechanisms need to be implemented to accommodate the dynamic nature of the ETP sequencing, while making efficient use of the ATE resources.

Design Phase. Starting in the design phase, the test programmer needs a tool that will assist in the development of test programs. See Figure 3. The tool should have the following properties:

- selection of test strategy type to be employed
 - Fault Isolation (FI) strategy only
 - Fault Detection (FD) strategy only
 - a Fault Detection strategy leading into a Fault Isolation strategy (FD / FI)
- classification of the test types
 - Interface Device (ID) test
 - safe-to-power-on test
 - end-to-end test
 - diagnostic test
 - etc.
- identification of test sequencing constraints
 - safe-to-power-on tests follow ID tests
 - diagnostic tests follow end-to-end tests
 - test x before test y
 - etc.
- identification of atomic test requirements
 - atomic test descriptions (purpose, scope, etc.)
 - test stimulus, measurement, and sequencing requirements
 - failure mode coverage
 - etc.
- identification of resource constraints
 - resource status preferences on initiating an encapsulated test
 - resource status at completion of an encapsulated test
 - etc.

The constraints must be satisfied by any test strategy that gets generated. The topological and logistic data, presently supported by the WSTA, combined with these new data elements should provide all the information necessary for the tool to generate robust test strategies applicable to each level of maintenance. Design for testability FOMs would be based on these new test strategies, which will more accurately reflect the on-site testing and would be tailored to each level of maintenance.

FIGURE 3

Authoring Phase. During the authoring phase, the test programmer will use the information from the design tool as the basis for generating the test programs. Encapsulated test programs will be generated. An authoring tool will be used to establish the relationships between the test programs, the design tool data, and the test documentation in electronic format, much the same as is currently done with the IDSS ADA. The end product of this phase is a diagnostic data base which is independent of the target tester, with data that may be tailored to any maintenance level, and exhibits the encapsulated test program philosophy of dynamic test sequencing.

Test Operation Phase. During the operation phase, the ATE execution environment must implement the ETP approach. The diagnostic data base generated during the authoring phase is provided to the test site. The ATE test executive will interface with an "ADS-like" diagnostic reasoner. This reasoner will work like the IDSS ADS by providing the recommended next best test to the test executive. The test executive will in turn provide the results of the test. In recommending the next

best test, the reasoner will utilize not only the topological and logistics data, but will also use the test classifications, test sequencing constraints, and the resource constraints in determining the recommended test for the selected test strategy type. This interaction between the test executive and the diagnostic reasoner will continue until the ATE either finds the IUT has no faults, or identifies a fault to the lowest level replaceable unit or ambiguity group.

Verification and Validation. One of the largest concerns with applying this new process is how to validate the resultant Test Programs. Since the resultant test program is no longer static, how do you verify that the TP is "good?" In order to have a high confidence level in the TPs generated by this new process, the TPS developer must have an equally high confidence in both the diagnostic engine and the dependency model driving the engine. This engine, being a common element, will not have to be verified for each application. The data that drives the engine, i.e., the dependency model, is the only variable.

The old adage of "Garbage in, Garbage out" once again applies to this model based approach to Test Programs. Just as a traditional Test Program developer can generate a "bad" test program, likewise, a test engineer can generate a "bad" dependency model. In the hopes of minimizing subjectivity, the government is in the process of conducting a joint effort with industry to establish a standard set of guidelines for developing dependency models. These guidelines should hopefully give the person acquiring or developing a dependency model a higher level of confidence that his resultant model is both complete and accurate. Also, a higher level of confidence in the dependency model is obtained if the model was derived from or compared against the Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA).

Making Modifications. When a change is made to an IUT, a corresponding change will be required to be made to the IUT Test Program. Since the Test Program is now based on a diagnostic model of the IUT and the ETP approach, when an Engineering Change is made to the IUT the effectivity of the change is well defined. Changes to the dependency model and

the ETPs associated with the changed hardware must be made. The new model and ETPs are then added to or replaced within the data base, and then the data is revalidated.

BENEFITS

Table 1 illustrates estimated time savings, which would relate directly to cost savings, by applying the above described process for Test Program development versus the traditional approach to generating TPs. The TPS Development Task categories and present time allocations were extracted from a Consolidated Automated Support System (CASS) TPS cost study prepared for the Naval Underwater Systems Center[5]. Since the study was based on historical data, the baseline for this analysis assumes no structured or effective Testability Program was implemented for the IUTs. As shown, 39 percent of the original time is saved. The following paragraphs discuss where the potential savings are gained within each development task.

TPS Development Task	Percent Time Allotted	
	<i>Present Process</i>	<i>New Process</i>
Data Analysis	5	1
Test Strategy	10	1
DFC/TPI	25	22
Code/Compile	10	4
ID Design/Integration	35	23
Acceptance	15	10
Savings	-	39

TABLE 1. TPS DEVELOPMENT TIME SAVINGS

Data Analysis. The Data Analysis task consists of familiarization and analysis of both the IUT and target ATE. For the purpose of this analysis, the cost required to generate the dependency models was not included. This cost was not-included based upon the assumption that, for future weapon system acquisitions utilizing concurrent engineering principles and

sound testability techniques, the dependency model will be generated during the design phase of the IUT, and will therefore be an input to the TP development process.

Test Strategy Generation. For the traditional test strategy generation phase, the TPS developer identifies the specific test approaches to be performed on the IUT. The result is a complete Fault Detection and Fault Isolation program set which is derived from the source documentation. Savings can be realized by applying WSTA or similar tools that generate effective, automated Fault Isolation Strategies. However, even further savings are realizable by applying the new concept which incorporates Fault Detection Strategies.

Diagnostic Flow Chart (DFC) and Test Program Instruction (TPI). After completion of the Test Strategy, the TPS developer generates a Detailed Flow Chart (DFC) of the proposed test strategy. The DFC details all information required for generating the proper ATE Code. In addition to the DFC, a preliminary Test Program Instruction (TPI) is developed during this phase. The TPI provides TPS related information needed for testing in addition to information necessary to execute and analyze the TPS. The savings identified in this TPS development area are conservatively estimated and are due to the early attention to test requirements.

Code and Compile. The TPS developer generates the error-free syntax for the diagnostic program that is executable on the target ATE. Using the new process, this task either consists of coding and compiling ETPs, or pulling existing ETPs from an established library. Near-term savings will be immediately realized by elimination of coding "hard" test strategies. Additional long-term benefits will be due to the potential reuse of Encapsulated Test Programs.

Interface Device (ID) Design and TPS Integration/Debug. The ID Design and TPS Integration phase is the most intense phase in the TPS development effort, bringing together the three parts of the TPS (i.e., TP, ID, TPI). The goal is to demonstrate TPS effectiveness. Physical faults are inserted into the IUT and the TP executed to determine if the corrective action

specified returns the IUT to Ready-for-Issue (RFI) status. The new process has very little effect on the design of the ID, however, the savings identified in the integration phase are conservatively estimated and are due to the early attention to test requirements during the IUT design phase.

Acceptance Testing. Having completed the Integration/Debug Phase, the TPS developer is required to demonstrate the TPS effectiveness to a minimum acceptance level. This phase demonstrates to the customer the quality of the product. Although the amount of time involved in fully demonstrating the TPS should not be reduced by applying the new process, the number of "surprises", and hence the number of required modifications to the Test Program, should be drastically reduced.

CONCLUSION

By applying a sound concurrent approach to weapon system diagnostic design, we can assure the timely and affordable development of highly effective test programs. Within the IDSS framework, this can be best achieved by continued support and improvement of the IDSS tool set, which can evolve in step with industry standards and expectations.

Perhaps the most significant industry effort being followed is the Artificial Intelligence and Expert System Tie to Automatic Test Equipment (AI-ESTATE). "AI-ESTATE will define the interfaces between a reasoner and the reasoning system users as well as test equipment, test information knowledge bases and more conventional databases. Interfaces associated with system test and diagnosis include those that exist between hardware (automatic test equipment, unit under test), users (developers, end users) and software (test programs, databases, knowledge bases)." [6] It is the goal of the IDSS program to ensure that its tool set is in compliance with any data standards established by this group. By combining industry standard diagnostic libraries and data standards with the non-proprietary tool set, the diagnostic community can achieve the maximum benefits.

The authors have presented an approach to developing and implementing test programs that may bridge the testability analysis / test program gap. The Navy's IDSS program provides the framework for the concept. Although a formal effort to demonstrate the concept has not commenced, the authors hope to see the potential of the approach realized in the future.

REFERENCES

1. Integrated Diagnostic Support System (IDSS) Weapon System Testability Analyzer Program Design Specification, CI Document No. PDBL - IDSTA01F, Contract No. N00024-87-C-4033.
2. Bearse, T., "Integrated Diagnostics Support System (IDSS) Fault Isolation Reasoners," *WESCON/92 Conference Record*, Anaheim, California, November 1992.
3. Bearse, T., "Integrated Diagnostics Support System (IDSS) Artificial Intelligence Applications," *Proceedings of Artificial Intelligence Applications for Acquisition Management, Logistics Management, and Personnel Management*, Williamsburg, Virginia, March-April 1992.
4. Integrated Diagnostic Support System (IDSS) Adaptive Diagnostic Subsystem (ADS) Program Design Specification, CI Document No. PDBL - IDSAD01D, Contract No. N00024-87-C-4033.
5. The Consolidated Automated Support System (CASS) Cost Benefit Analysis, Volume III: TPS Requirements for Augmented Family of Test (AFOT) Systems, Revision 1.0, 15 May 1992; Prepared for the Naval Underwater Systems Center, Newport, RI; Prepared by Prospective Computer Analysts, Inc., Roslyn, New York.
6. Proposed IEEE Standard 1232.1 Data and Knowledge Specifications for Artificial Intelligence and Expert System Tie to Automatic Test Equipment (AI-ESTATE), Draft 3.2, 5 April 1993.